

Square Planar and Octahedral Complexes of Nickel(II) with 14-Membered and 21-Membered Macrocyclic Ligands Derived from Benzil and Carbohydrazide

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REACTION of nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate with benzil ($C_6H_5-CO-CO-C_6H_5$) and carbohydrazide ($NH_2-NH-CO-NH-NH_2$) in anhydrous methanol provides two different products. One is a deep red compound, slightly soluble in chloroform only and the other is a yellowish-green product soluble in polar organic solvents. The red compound is diamagnetic whereas the yellowish-green compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 3.16$ B.M.).

Square planar stereochemistry for the red compound and pseudo octahedral structure for the yellowish green compound are suggested from elemental analyses, vibrational spectra, solid state electronic spectra, magnetic properties and conductivity data. Available evidence suggests that in both the cases the nitrogen atoms act as donors.

Experimental

Preparation of carbohydrazide, $NH_2-NH-CO-NH-NH_2$, has been described earlier¹.

Preparation of the red coloured nickel(II) compound: Benzil (0.02 mol) was dissolved in anhydrous warm methanol (50 ml). Nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate (0.01 mol) in anhydrous methanol (10 ml) was added to this solution and the resulting clear solution was refluxed on a steam bath for a few minutes. This solution was added dropwise to a hot solution of carbohydrazide (0.02 mol) in anhydrous methanol (100 ml). The reaction mixture was then refluxed on steam bath. The colour of the mixture gradually changed to green-red. After 7-8 hr, fine needles of a deep red crystalline compound started separating out. Refluxing was continued for another 3 hr, then the solution was cooled and filtered. The deep red compound was washed first with hot water and then with rectified spirit and dried over silica gel. The compound is insoluble in all organic solvents but is only slightly soluble in chloroform. (Found: C, 61.45; H, 3.48; N, 19.35; Ni, 9.6; Cl, nil. Calcd. for (I); C, 61.58; H, 3.76; N, 19.15; Ni, 10.0%; Cl, nil).

Preparation of the yellowish-green compound: The filtrate obtained after the separation of the red compound (I) was again filtered to get rid of any of the red compound that might have accumulated. This filtrate was dried in a vacuum desiccator. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of ice cooled anhydrous methanol. Any

unreacted carbohydrazide (which is insoluble in cold methanol) separating out at this stage was filtered off and anhydrous acetone was added to the filtrate. Greenish-yellow compound that separated out was repeatedly purified by dissolving in cold methanol and precipitating with acetone. The product was finally dried over silica gel. (Found: C, 54.25; H, 4.6; N, 17.1; Cl, 7.3; Ni, 6.02; H_2O , 6.80. Calcd. for (II); C, 54.8; H, 4.4; N, 17.06; Cl, 7.2; Ni, 5.96; H_2O , 6.82%).

The techniques of analyses and physical measurements were the same as described in our earlier papers.

Results and Discussion

The infrared spectrum of carbohydrazide shows bands at 3360, 3200 and 3300 cm^{-1} . These are assigned to asymmetric $\nu(N-H)$, symmetric $\nu(N-H)$ vibrations of the NH_2 group and the secondary $-NH$ group, respectively². The $C=O$ stretch of the carbohydrazide appears as a strong broad absorption band centered at about 1635 cm^{-1} . The infrared spectrum of benzil contains a weak band at 3060 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $-CH$ stretching frequency associated with aromatic rings³. In addition to this, two bands appear at 1650 and 1595 cm^{-1} . The absorption bands at 1650 cm^{-1} and 1595 cm^{-1} are assigned to $C=O$ group stretching of benzil and aromatic vibration, respectively⁴. The infrared spectrum of the red nickel(II) complex (I) shows bands at 3170, 3060, 1665 and 1550 cm^{-1} . These are assigned to the secondary $-NH$, $-CH$ stretching frequency associated with benzene ring, aromatic ring vibration and the stretching frequency of the $C=N$ group, respectively^{5,6}. The $C=N$ band appears at a lower frequency due to the coordination of $C=N$ group to the metal ion. The stretching frequency of $\nu(C=O)$ completely disappears in the red complex indicating that enolisation has taken place (cf: I).

The ir spectrum of the greenish-yellow compound (II) shows a broad band centered at about 3200 cm^{-1} . This band appears to be a composite one due to $-CH$ stretching, secondary $-NH$ and water molecules. There is also a strong broad band at 1650-1660 cm^{-1} . It is well known that the stretching frequency of $C=O$ increases in a complex if it is not coordinated^{6,7}. The band at 1650-1660 cm^{-1} is assigned as a composite of the benzene ring vibration and $\nu(C=O)$ group of the carbohydrazide. The ir spectrum of the complex (II) also shows a moderately intense band at 1590 cm^{-1} which is attributed to the $C=N$ stretch in the yellowish-green complex. In view of the above infrared spectra, it may be concluded that in both the complexes all coordination sites are occupied by the nitrogen atoms of the $C=N$ groups.

Electronic spectra, magnetic moments and conductivity: The red nickel(II) complex is diamagnetic and its analysis (total absence of chlorine) indicates that the ligand has suffered deprotonation,

thus resulting in a neutral complex. The electronic spectrum (in nujol mull) shows bands at 18.5 kK and 20 kK. No other electronic transitions are observed below 10 kK. Square planar stereochemistry is thus suggested for the red nickel(II) complex⁸. Due to its extreme insolubility in common organic solvents, conductance measurements was not feasible. The yellowish-green nickel(II) complex shows three bands at 10.26, 16.0 and 26.3 kK. These bands are assignable to ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (ν_2), ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3) transitions, respectively. The ratio of $\nu_3 : \nu_1$ is 1.56 indicating an octahedral environment⁹ around the metal ion. There are also two weak bands at 18.52 and 20 kK. These are assigned to the two spin forbidden transitions ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ and ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$, respectively. From the transitions ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 , we get $10 Dq = 10.26 \text{ kK}$; $B' = 910 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\beta = 0.87$ (free ion B value = 1041 cm^{-1}). Bivalent electrolytic nature of the yellowish-green nickel(II) complex is indicated by the molar conductance ($\Delta_M = 157 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in methanol¹⁰. Magnetic moment value ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.16 \text{ B.M.}$) also lends support to an octahedral configuration.

The mass spectrum of the red diamagnetic complex (I) clearly shows the parent ion (m/e) peak at 584 (monomer molecular weight 584.17).

References

1. R. L. DUTTA and A. K. SARKAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 2557.
2. M. ALI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1785.
3. N. L. ALPERT, W. E. KRISER and H. A. SZYMOSKI, "Theory and Practices of Infrared Spectroscopy", Rosette Edition, 1963.
4. C. W. YOUNG and R. B. DUVAL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 709.
5. H. STRECK and E. ZIELER, *Monatsch Chem.*, 1966, **97**, 1131.
6. M. MASHIMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1962, **35**, 1882.
7. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 3rd Ed., 1966.
8. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
9. R. L. CARLIN, "Transition Metal Chemistry", Marcel Dekker, 1968, Vol. 4.
10. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.

Stabilisation of Salicylidene Amino Acids by Magnesium(II)

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THE salicylideneamino acid Schiff bases (I) are known to be unstable enough in the absence of a suitable metal ion¹. Quite stable complexes of these ligands with copper(II)², nickel(II)³, cobalt(II)⁴, manganese(II)⁵, (III)⁶ and zinc(II)^{7,8} are well established. The enhanced stability has been ascribed to the two chelate rings at the metal ion¹. We now report that a similar stabilisation effect has been observed in the presence of magnesium(II). Very few magnesium(II) complexes with tridentate ligands are known. A survey reveals the characterisation of six-coordinate magnesium(II) complexes with tridentate Schiff bases, acetylaceton-1-amidino-O-alkylurea⁹ and salicylidene aroyl (heteroaroyl) hydrazones⁹. The Schiff bases stabilised in the present investigation are salicylidene-glycine [salglyH₂] (I) and salicylidene- α -alanine [sal- α -alanH₂].

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